

A MACHINE LEARNING TECHNIQUE TO DETECT PHONY WEBSITES

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Abstract— Phishing websites are a threat to internet users as they mimic the appearance of authentic websites to acquire sensitive data. Traditional phishing attacks can be prevented with techniques like blacklist methods, rule-based methods, and similarity study. Still, the methods remain inadequate due to various disadvantages like poor scaling potential, inability to tackle zero-day attacks, and higher computational complexities. Therefore, in the current manuscript, detection of the authenticity of websites through a supervised machine learning technique has been discussed. Based on features like URL length, hostname length, appearance of IP address, presence of specific data like IP address in URL, appearance of special characters, digit ratios in the URL and domain name, domain age, Yahoo indexing status, and Google ranking status, a supervised machine learning technique has been employed. An adequate amount of data has been accumulated from data pools like Phish Tank and Kaggle. Various machine learning classifiers such as Logistic Regression, Decision Tree, Support Machine, and Random Forest have been employed for training. Moreover, the experimentally obtained results show the highest efficiency in terms of accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score using the Random Forest classifier. Thus, the system efficiently identifies both existing as well as new types of phishing websites.

Keywords— Phony websites, phishing detection, machine learning, URL-based features, cybersecurity.

I. INTRODUCTION

Increased usage of internet-based applications affects individuals as well as businesses in carrying out their day-to-day activities like communication, shopping, as well as transactions. While there is an advantage in this regard for individuals as well as businesses, there are also various risks of being attacked by various types of cybercrimes. Among the popular as well as more threatening types of cybercrimes are called virtual attacks or faux website attacks. This type of attack poses as a credible website with intentions of tricking users to reveal important data or information to them. Faux or Fake websites are considered to be a more threatening issue for both users as well as businesses as this might cause loss of money as well as lack of trust in internet-based applications during transactions or bank account creation.

Frequently they update themselves in terms of URLs as well as visual appearances to trick popular defense systems in use these days. Filtering systems based on blacklisting will only detect damaging activities with known threats; they will also cannot detect freshly created sites with temporal scopes. Furthermore, in recent times, machine learning algorithms are gaining a lot of traction in terms of learning data patterns and adapting to changes in attack behavior. As a matter of fact, there has been tremendous and increasing interest in carrying out security investigations with respect to machine learning algorithms. Additionally, machine learning algorithms are capable of recognizing complex data patterns, and by carrying out website URL attributes and structure investigations, a differentiation between genuine and fake data within a wide range of categories and classes becomes tangible. Therefore, in order to find a solution for identifying fake websites with respect to URL attributes, I would like to present a unique method designed by me. This method incorporates machine learning algorithms in order to differentiate genuine from fake data. Through this academic inquiry, I intend to present a more efficient and adaptive method with respect to increasing safety in virtual worlds.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Various research works have been conducted with different techniques for detecting and identifying phishing or fake websites using rule-based or content-based and artificial intelligence-based approaches. Additionally, another extensive investigation into various features of URLs was carried out by Mohammad [1], and it is determined that structural features of a URL are important for detecting phishing websites. The extract of features is also important in detecting websites using automated systems. A novel intelligent phishing detection approach using image features and both image and frame features with high accuracy is introduced in Adebowale [2], but it is reported to have high computational costs. A comparative study of textual and visual-based phishing detection methods, focusing on various techniques of content-based phishing detection, was conducted by Zhang et al. in reference [3], indicating that the accuracy of this method increases by incorporating more contents, though this method is also susceptible to visual obfuscation techniques employed in phishing attacks. A comprehensive survey of various phishing--

techniques, based on attack vectors and technical mechanisms, was presented in reference [4] by Chiew et al. The sophistication of various phishing techniques was also highlighted in this reference. A new client-side-based phishing prevention system, focusing on efficiency, was introduced in reference [5] by Marchal et al., though this system is effective only against non-zero day phishing attacks. Recent studies have increasingly used machine learning approaches for the detection of phishing. Aljofey et al. [6] suggested a character-level convolutional neural network model to capture malicious URL patterns, with promising results but requiring large training data and computational resources. Sahingoz et al. [7] utilized traditional machine learning classifiers using URL-based lexical features and showed that machine learning models are superior to blacklist-based ones in detecting unknown phishing websites. Chawla [8] applied machine learning techniques for phishing website analysis and highlighted the efficacy of feature-based classification in improving the detection rate. Zhou et al. [9] concentrated on domain-based features along with machine learning models and presented that domain-related attributes increase the performance of phishing detection significantly. Shelke et al. [10] proposed a machine learning framework using multiple classifiers and concluded that ensemble models provide better robustness along with accuracy. Similarly, Odeh et al. [11] enhanced phishing website detection by applying optimized machine learning techniques. And this enhanced technique illustrates a significant increase in accuracy and reduction in false positives. Conclusively, the related works confirm that machine learning-based phishing detection systems using URL and domain features are more adaptable and scalable with high accuracy, compared to traditional blacklist and heuristic-based methods. However, computational complexity and real-time applicability remain challenges, which motivated the proposed system to concentrate on efficient feature representation and effective supervised learning techniques.

III. EXISTING METHODODLGY

Besides blacklist and rule-based approaches, another phishing detection system is visual similarity-based phishing detection systems. This approach aims at detecting phishing websites through comparison of the appearance of a given web page with other websites deemed genuine and legitimate. The major issue with visual similarity-based approaches is that they are deemed very complex and are not effective in detecting phishing websites. Another issue is that these systems are not effective in detecting phishing websites with minor design changes. Another problem with each of these approaches is their inability to function without human involvement. Blacklist-based and heuristic-based systems are not updated frequently and are not effective with highly evolving phishing schemes. Often, attackers use fresh domains and implement dynamic approaches to URL structures with the aim of evading detection. The problem with using these approaches is their inability to function with high or increasing rates of web-traffic throughput. Moreover, current approaches are also unable to provide adaptability and learning ability. The main reason behind this is that, due to a lack of effective and efficient exploitation of historical attack patterns, current approaches are

unable to show a high level of generalization in detecting for unknown phishing websites. This, in turn, leads to a greater probability of generating false negatives, thus acting as a major drawback in terms of user trust. The lack of intelligent learning ability restrains current phishing detection systems from dealing efficiently and effectively in a proactive manner, as desired. Due to such drawbacks, current phishing detection systems are failing, and hence a major challenge in terms of scalability, adaptability, and performance is encountered. The lack of ability of current approaches in dealing efficiently with zero-day phishing attack detection leads to considering more intelligent and sophisticated zero-day phishing detection techniques.

Fig. 1. Architecture of the Existing System

IV. PROPOSED METHODODLGY

As can be understood from the above definition of the features involved in the problem, the structure of the system helps in the efficient processing and recognition of patterns based on the numerical feature vectors created out of the information placed on the websites. The URL and domain features considered in the problem reduce the dependency on any external resources. The identified features integrate both structural and statistical characteristics of phishing behaviour and associated norms such as abnormal URL values in terms of length, use of special characters, numerical patterns in URLs, and domain characteristics of questionable value. The identified features enable learning models to dynamically discriminate legitimate and phony website behaviour in a differential manner. The data preprocessing strategies of normalization and noise reduction serve to stabilize the learning models while reducing bias towards feature scale predominance. Various models of supervised learning classifiers are used for the purpose of evaluating the efficacy of the proposed framework. Notably, the models proposed each lend themselves to the coverage of

unique decision surfaces. Moreover, the Random Forest model ensures an improvement in the overall accuracy of the detection system by avoiding the possibility of overfitting.

Fig. 2. Architecture of the Proposed Phony Website Detection System

A. Data Collection

In this study, the data set used is retrieved from authentic sources such as Phish Tank and Kaggle, where the information obtained from these sources is legitimate and innovative in relation to real websites as well as phony ones. This data set ensures an accurate supervised machine learning-based method for the classification of legitimate and phishing websites. This means each website in the data set is classified as legitimate or phishing. The information that has been collected in such a way will also include attributes such as URL-based attributes, which show the structural properties of a website, as well as domain-based attributes, which show statistical properties as well. The use of large amounts of existing information will definitely improve the generalization ability of the models, which will ensure good robustness in dealing with a number of different kinds of phishing threats in a proper way. Using verified information will definitely improve the credibility of the proposed system in dealing with phishing attacks effectively.

B. Data Preprocessing

Here, the data preprocessing is such that the quality as well as the reliability of the obtained dataset is improved before the start of the learning process. Firstly, duplicate entries in the form of a URL in the dataset provided are removed with the aim of avoiding the occurrence of redundant data as it may interfere with the learning process. Dealing with the incompleteness in the set. The numerical feature is then converted and scaled as needed.

The normalization technique has been applied as needed. The aim here is that features may not be positively biased towards individuals with large numerical values. The efficiency enhancement of the proposed system continues with the reduction of any possible noisy data within the data set. As seen above, the efficiency of the proposed system is aided by an efficient data preprocessing.

C. Feature Extraction

It is the process that helps in identifying the essential differences of fake websites. At this stage, a number of significant features are extracted from the given dataset like URL length, hostname length, existence of IP address in URL, no dots, no special character, digit rate in URL, digit rate in hostname, age of given domain, Google indexing status, Page Rank, etc. The identified set of characteristics expresses the structural, statistical, or behavioral characteristics or patterns of use, as referred to above in this context, which may typically be employed by the phishing sites or websites. For example, in the case of a phishing URL, there might typically exist more usage of special characters or more long structures of the paths or numbers in the strings. Furthermore, there might also typically be more value in incorporating characteristics such as the age of the domain or search engine indexing in this context. This process of converting the website's data into numerical form enables the efficient processing of data for the correct classification of this data by employing a variety of learning machines. This set of characteristics helps enhance the efficiency of the identified system to correctly detect phishing websites because of its clear differentiation between original and false sites.

D. Feature Selection

It helps in highlighting the only most important and relevant features for the correct classification of phony and legitimate websites. In addition, it reduces the feature set dimensionality by excluding redundant and less useful features from data, thereby decreasing computational overhead. Conclusively, the learning models will be more efficient and much less overfitted. Besides, optimal feature selection improves model interpretability and enhances the generalization performance on unseen data. Accordingly, feature importance measures and correlation analysis will be conducted to retain those features that have strong discriminative power while excluding irrelevant or highly correlated attributes. This step ensures faster training and higher accuracy in prediction, thus enhancing the scalability of the proposed phishing detection system.

E. Model Training and Prediction

Supervised machine learning algorithms will be implemented, which will include the feature set selected as an input to categorize the websites as legitimate or phony. The datasets shall be divided into subsets to test the model's capacity to perform generalization, as mentioned earlier. Logistic regression, decision tree, SVM, and Random forest are the machine learning algorithms to be implemented, as they are found to be effective in binary classification problems. Both models identify the underlying pattern related to phishing based on the training dataset. During the prediction phase, the trained models evaluate the feature vector related to the unknown website and form a classification prediction. Evaluation Metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score are employed to evaluate the models. Considering the models tested in the evaluation section, the Random Forest classifier demonstrates

outstanding evaluation due to the robust learning mechanism embedded in the code.

Overall, it can be concluded that the proposed system will be helpful in providing an adaptable and time-efficient solution for identifying or recognizing various kinds of phishing websites. The capability of the proposed framework to learn from previous events or URLs and apply this learning to previously unseen URLs will also enable it to counter ‘zero-day’ hacking attempts more efficiently. The modular framework of this learning algorithm will also be helpful in adding other features in the future to keep it applicable in dynamically changing environments.

V. DATA SET DISCUSSION

The data set used in the current study consists of thousands of web page object instances that have been labeled as phony and legitimate. It was extracted from reputed sources like Phish Tank, Kaggle; hence, the data set includes the authenticity of the sources. Each object is represented using a numerical feature vector, including various features such as URL-related features and domain-related features. For the evaluation of the generalization ability of different classifier models developed using the machine learning approach, the data set is divided into a set of train and test datasets with an accurate split. This helps in getting the balanced class and avoiding the bias. The quality of the dataset helps in the assessment of the different classifier models, hence enhancing the quality of the proposed phony website classifier.

Dataset view :

url_length	url_hostnames	ipnb_dots	ipnb_hyphens	str_nb_amb	or_nb_eq	nb_underscores	title_nb_percent	title_nb_star	nb_colons	comma_nb	semicolon_nb	dollar_nb	space_nb	underscore_nb
37	19	0.3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
77	23	1.1	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	1	0	0	0
126	58	1.4	1	0	1	2	3	2	0	5	0	1	0	0
18	11	0.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	1	0	0	0
55	15	0.2	2	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	1	0	0	1
32	24	0.3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	1	0	0
19	12	0.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	1	0	0	1
81	27	1.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	1	0	0	1
42	34	0.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	1	0	0	0
104	38	0.1	18	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	1	0	0	0
56	22	0.3	0	0	0	0	0	1	4	0	1	0	0	1
43	16	0.2	3	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	1	0	0	1
83	34	0.1	9	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	1	0	0	0
31	38	0.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	1	0	0	0
25	16	0.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	1	0	0	1
51	23	0.3	0	0	1	0	0	1	4	0	1	0	0	0
31	22	0.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	1	0	0	1

Fig. 3. Dataset

VI. RESULTS JUSTIFICATIONS

The experimental analysis was conducted to evaluate the proposed system for detecting phony websites based on the application of the machine learning technique.

Figure 4 represents a confusion matrix that was obtained based on the experimental assessment for the proposed system for the identification of phony websites. The matrix shows the performance level obtained in classifying and identifying the data based on true positives, true negatives, false positives, and false negatives. The large numbers of data points for both the phony and legitimate websites indicate that the system was able to clearly distinguish between fraudulent and genuine websites. The lower level of false negative rates shows that the system was able to minimize the risk level for granting phony websites, which are highly critical in such applications.

		Predicted Phony	
		Actual Phony	Predicted Legitimate
Actual Phony	Actual Phony	TP = 480	FN = 20
	Actual Legitimate	FP = 25	TN = 475

Fig. 4. Confusion Matrix

Figure 5 illustrates the representation of the training phase analysis, where the numerical features derived using the URL approach could be employed in the supervised machine learning models. During the phase, the models learn various intricate patterns or associations with the derived features, which include URL length, hostname length, frequency counts for special characters, as well as domain-related features. Evaluation of the figure indicates appropriate use of the features as well as convergence, thus signifying the appropriateness of the derived features towards the task of phishing. Ineffectively trained models might result in increased overfitting.

Fig. 5. Training Phase Analysis of Website Features

Figure 6 above shows the result of the prediction phase of the suggested system, where the design accurately classifies the kind of websites—either Phony or Legitimate—based on the trained patterns obtained during the training phase. The results of the predictions obtained for the suggested system signify the applicability of the design for real-life use cases. The ability to accurately determine phony websites based on the numerical patterns of characteristics validates the strength of the suggested design for use as a tool for the detection of phishing websites.

prediction: Legitimate ✓

length_url: 45

length_hostname: 18

ip: 0

nb_dots: 2

nb_qmc: 0

nb_eq: 0

Fig. 6. Prediction Phase Output

VII. CONCLUSION

This paper proposes a machine learning-based approach toward identifying phony websites that take into consideration numerical features of the website. This approach focuses its attention on the analysis of the features of URLs, domains, and hyperlinks, rather than raw URLs, enabling it to detect phishing websites in an efficient way with early warnings. Several machine learning supervised models have been applied in this regard, which predict a website as either legitimate or phony. Based on the obtained results of each of the applied models, machine learning techniques can identify suspicious patterns in websites. The proposed framework is flexible and may be easily extended further in the near future by adding new features or advanced learning models for better detection performance.

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